

MobiSpaces Impact Event

Advancing European
Mobility Data Innovation

Post-Event Report 23 June 2025

Funded by
the European Union

On 23 June 2025, the **MobiSpaces Impact Event** brought together stakeholders in Rome and online to mark the culmination of three years of research and innovation under the Horizon Europe programme. The event showcased the project's achievements in developing sustainable, privacy-preserving solutions for mobility data governance and use.

A Green and Intelligent Future for Mobility Data

MobiSpaces has delivered a holistic data governance platform that integrates AI-based operations, edge analytics, and federated learning. The platform enables decentralised, mobility-aware data processing while upholding green and privacy-first principles.

Project Coordinator [Matteo Falsetta \(GFT Technologies\)](#) opened the event by outlining the project's key goals and impact, including:

- ✦ Engagement with over 60,000 citizens through pilot activities and 550+ researchers.
- ✦ Recognition by the European Commission's Innovation Radar for six key innovations.
- ✦ Development of open-source tools and a modular architecture supporting trustworthy, efficient, and interoperable data spaces.

Real-World Impact: Use Case Highlights

The event also featured presentations from the project use cases:

iRoute - presented by [Enrico Buzzo \(ATM\)](#): managing over 900 buses (100+ electric) in Genoa (Italy). This use case focuses on predictive battery health and optimised scheduling to improve fleet efficiency and extend e-bus battery life.

SmartSense - presented by [Mario-Alexandru Mircea \(Bosch\)](#): this pilot addresses urban air quality by combining traffic volume data with simulations to estimate emissions and propose actionable recommendations to make Thessaloniki (Greece) a cleaner city.

CrowdSeaMapping - presented by [Niels Bo Nielsen \(Danish Geodata Agency\)](#): this use case leverages crowdsourced sensor data and Federated Learning to improve navigational safety through decentralised, privacy-preserving processing techniques.

These use cases demonstrated how MobiSpaces technologies support cities, transport operators, and maritime authorities in building smarter and more sustainable mobility ecosystems.

Technical Innovation at the Core

The project's technical leads were presented by [Claudia Mertinger \(Fujitsu\)](#) and [George Theodoropoulos \(University of Piraeus\)](#). They showed several core components of the MobiSpaces Toolkit, including:

- ✧ MobiBench for mobility data preprocessing and augmentation.
- ✧ FLP (Future Location Prediction) for privacy-preserving, edge-based trajectory forecasting.
- ✧ MobiEdge, a decentralised intelligence framework built for autonomy, resilience, and cost-effectiveness.

Together, these components empower organisations to process mobility data at the edge while maintaining high levels of privacy and efficiency.

Panel Discussion: Building Europe's Mobility Data Spaces

A high-level panel, moderated by [Roberta Fabrizi \(Trust-IT Services\)](#), brought together experts from [Gaia-X 4FutureMobility \(Johannes Unruh\)](#), the [TANGO \(Lauresha Toska\)](#) and [TEADAL \(Pierluigi Plebani\)](#) projects, and the MobiSpaces consortium. Discussions explored:

- ✦ **Data Spaces Deployment:** European data spaces are transitioning from pilots to deployment. Yet, market readiness and cross-domain interoperability remain critical challenges.
- ✦ **Gaia-X Learnings:** Projects like NeMo.Bil demonstrate the power of modular, open-source solutions and the importance of robust documentation. Build on what already exists.
- ✦ **Open Source & FAIR Data:** Metadata standards and clear documentation are still lacking. Strong governance and privacy-by-design are essential for broader adoption.
- ✦ **Policy & Regulation:** There's a need for fewer bureaucratic hurdles and more interoperable frameworks. A user-centric approach is key to driving innovation.
- ✦ **Looking Ahead:** The potential is immense - especially if Europe delivers on the promise of interconnected, decentralised data spaces. International perspectives and collaboration will be vital.

Co-Creation Workshop for Future Exploitation

The afternoon featured a Co-Creation Workshop with the [MobiSpaces External Stakeholder Expert Board \(ESEB\)](#), focusing on the sustainability of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Discussions covered:

- ✦ Adoption strategies and target markets for MobiSpaces innovations.
- ✦ Integration into existing workflows and development of hybrid software/hardware models.
- ✦ The need for measurable societal, environmental, and economic impacts.
- ✦ Importance of simplified communication and a shared platform for future exploitation.

Stakeholders emphasised the role of communities and vertical industry actors in ensuring these tools reach operational scale.

Did you miss the event?

The full recording is available on the [MobiSpaces YouTube channel](#).

A blue banner with white and red text and graphics. It features the MobiSpaces logo, a date box for 'FINAL EVENT 23 June 2025 from 09:30 to 16:00 (CEST)', a large red play button icon, and the event title 'MobiSpaces Impact Event'. Below the title is the subtitle 'Advancing European Mobility Data Innovation'. The banner also includes several circular icons representing mobility data and a 'Funded by the European Union' logo in the bottom right corner.

MobiSpaces

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Follow MobiSpaces on the main project's social media channels and visit the website to follow its technical advancements.

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